

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Addition of MicroCAT to the SAMBA array

Milestone MS11

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Milestone report

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Cover sheet: Pictures of Pressure Inverted Echo Sounders, of the CTD Rosette of the Brazilian Navy and the two Research Vessels that deployed the Eastern (South African RV Algoa) and Western (Brazilian RV Antares) SAMBA mooring array. Credits: Olga Sato and Tarron Lamont.

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1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

Four instruments measuring Temperature and Salinity were deployed on four bottom moorings during two different campaigns to the eastern (South Africa) and western South Brazil continental slope-abyssal plains intersections along the SAMBA mooring array, positioned at 34° 30' S (Fig. 1).

Fig.1: Status of the SAMBA west array from 2009 to 2025.

2. Work performed and main achievements

We had planned two cruises along the eastern and western SAMBA array moorings to recover and redeploy all the bottom moorings that are either Pressure Inverted Echo Sounder (PIES) or Current-meter Pressure Inverted Echo Sounder (CPIES). The two deepest moorings for each eastern and western array were planned to include one MicroCATS instrument each to measure, during two years, the bottom ocean temperature and salinity. These deployments were planned and undertaken by the SAMBA scientific partners, who are external to the OCEANICE project. The eastern boundary mooring array is maintained by the South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment in collaboration with the US (NOAA-AOML) and France (ENS and Ifremer). The western SAMBA mooring array is maintained by Argentina (Servicio de Hidrografía Naval and University of Buenos Aires), Brazil (University of São Paulo), and the US (NOAA-AOML).

Fig. 2: SBE37 Microcat installation. Credit Photo: Gavin Louw, DEFF, South Africa.

2.1 Deployment of two MicroCATS in the abyssal plain along the eastern SAMBA array

The South African RV Algoa sailed on the 18th of September 2023 to recover the full SAMBA-East Pressure Inverted Echo Sounder (PIES) moorings deployed during the SAMBA 2021 cruise, service these moorings, and redeploy them until September 2025. A total of 10 PIES were deployed along the SAMBA transect at 34°30 S and between 17° E and 0° during the SAMBA 2021 cruise (moorings P1, P2, P3, P3a, P4, P4a, P5, P6, P7 & P8 in Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Schematic maps indicating the area of operation along the SAMBA transect, relative to South Africa, and off Hondeklip Bay.

The following PIES have been deployed with MicroCATs attached.

Table 1: PIES along the eastern SAMBA array instrumented with MicroCATs

Station S/N	Time and Deployment Position	Sounder	Prog. depth	Meas. Period
PIES8 052 + MicroCat	26/09/2023 03:00 S34°30.0581 E00° 00.1127	4597m	4595m	4 pings x10 min. P&T 20min
PIES3a 066 + MicroCat	01/10/2023 22:11 S34°30.0096 E15°47.3118	4227m	4300m	4 pings x 10 min. P&T 20min

2.2 Deployment of two MicroCATS in the abyssal plain along the western SAMBA array

The Brazilian Navy RV Antares sailed on the 2nd of June 2025 to recover the SAMBA-West PIES and CPIES moorings deployed during the SAMOC 2022 cruise, service these moorings, and redeploy them till September 2026. A total of four PIES and 4CPIES were serviced and redeployed or deployed along the SAMBA West transect at 34°30 S during the 2025 cruise (PIES A, B, C, and D and CPIES OA, AA, BB, CC in Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Location of the PIES (A, B, C, and D) and CPIES (OA, AA, BB, CC) of the SAMBA West line (34.5°S) superposed on sea surface temperature (top) and sea surface salinity from the World Ocean Atlas 2018.

The following PIES and CPIES have been deployed with MicroCATs attached.

Table 2: PIES and CPIES along the western SAMBA array instrumented with MicroCats

Station S/N	Time and Deployment Position	Sounder	Prog. depth	Meas. Period
PIES D + MicroCat	06/06/2025 20:30 (GMT) 34° 28.989'S 44° 29.799'W	4756 m	4750 m	4 pings x 10 min. P&T 20min
CPIES CC + MicroCat	06/06/2025 10:35 (GMT) 34° 30.019'S 46° 05.422'W	4730 m	4750 m	4 pings x 10 min. P&T 20min

2.3 Open Science

The first data set will be available in January 2026, and it will be in open access.